

CHEMISTRY

DESTRUCTION OF THE PROCION RED MX-5B DYE IN A FLOW-THROUGH PLASMA REACTOR

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Abstract

This study investigated the plasmochemical degradation of Procion red MX-5B. A plasma electrochemical unit was utilised to detoxify wastewater that had been contaminated with Procion red MX-5B, with a modified plasma generating module. The experiments were performed using the galvanostatic mode with a current of 45 A and voltages ranging from 21 to 24 V. The concentration of Procion red MX-5B was ascertained through the use of UV-visible spectroscopy during plasma treatment.

Plasma-chemical treatment of Procion red MX-5B dye causes rapid destruction of its molecule, as discovered in our experiment. During the initial stage, the molecule cleaves into two aromatic fragments. Following the initial cleavage, degradation of intermediate aromatic compounds commences. The decomposition products resulting from the process have low toxicity and can be effectively neutralised through biological treatment methods.

Two types of carbon-containing degradation products are formed as a result of plasmochemical degradation of Procion red MX-5B. The first one is a finely dispersed hydrophobic material that, due to its low specific gravity, hydrophobicity and the inclusion of gas bubbles, floats and concentrates near the solution-air interface. The second type consists of larger and more hydrophilic particles and accumulates in the lower part of the cell by sedimentation.

Keywords: plasma chemical reactor, wastewater, Procion red MX-5B azo dye, destruction, micro-nanocarbon.

1. Introduction

The disposal of wastewater from dyes poses an urgent and unresolved environmental problem. The production and usage of dyes necessitate substantial volumes of water. On average, each tonne of dye consumes 200-250 m³ of water. The presently utilized dyes exhibit a high level of stability. The high chemical stability and light fastness of dyes, which are essential in dyeing technology, cause challenges in treating and disposing of wastewater generated by companies that manufacture or use dyes. Untreated wastewater disrupts the ecological balance of natural water bodies, which are sources of water supply, and exacerbates the negative impact on the environment caused by human activity. The majority of dyes are harmful to plant and animal life, with carcinogenic and mutagenic effects [1, 2]. Dyes in water sources also pose a risk to human health.

Several methods such as extraction, sorption-coagulation, membrane filtration, and biological treatments have been proposed for treating wastewaters containing dyes [3-6]. The application of these methods in some cases can lead to achieving high levels of purification. Nevertheless, these methods are limited by scientific, technical, and economic factors. For instance, adsorption on activated carbon is restricted only to water-soluble dyes, biodegradation might not be effective due to the biotoxicity of many dyes, and the use of aggressive and toxic reagents (such as ozonation, UV light, H₂O₂, Fenton's reagent, electrochemical oxidation) is required for treatment. The nomenclature of dyes is broad, and various types are challenging to neutralize. Dyes are frequently found in wastewater, mixed

with other organic and mineral components that pose obstacles in treatment. All the methods mentioned above require consumables such as oxidizing reagents, membranes, and sorbents, which increase the cost of the process and make it more complex. Utilizing such consumables results in the creation of secondary anthropogenic pollution in the form of spent sorbents, filtrates, concentrates, wash water, as well as poisoned and spent membranes. Therefore, the issues of treatment and disposal are replicated at another level. It is crucial to develop innovative non-waste technologies to address this problem comprehensively.

Thermal treatment is a promising method for treating such wastewater. Thermal destruction methods are universal, have simple hardware design and controls, and can be easily automated. Achieving high temperatures is a primary factor in effectively using thermal treatment for decomposing heat-resistant organic contaminants. Conventional methods struggle to use thermal destruction for large volumes of low-polluted wastewater due to considerable energy consumption for heating and water evaporation. Direct destruction in the liquid phase is preferable. This method reduces the energy consumption of phase transitions. High-temperature plasma treatment can effectively treat heat. The combined effects of high temperature, UV radiation photodestruction, and electrochemical redox processes can neutralise contaminants with high chemical stability.

The aim of this work is to study the destruction of the Procion red MX-5B dye in a flow-through plasma reactor.

2. Experimental procedure

A plasma electrochemical unit with a modified plasma generating module (see Fig. 1) was employed to destroy the dye by plasma-chemical conversion of waste water.

The electrode chamber, which is equipped with two electrodes, consists of a vertically mounted working (discharge) electrode coaxial to the tank and a horizontally mounted auxiliary electrode. The electrodes

are made of a refractory alloy based on chromium and tungsten. A device is implemented in the vertical electrode to control the immersion depth and distance from the horizontal electrode. This arrangement allows for efficient and uniform distribution of the electric field throughout the cell volume, resulting in smooth plasma torch burning and reduced power consumption. The solution to be treated is 1 L.

Fig. 1– Schematic of a plasma-chemical reactor for the degradation of Procion red MX-5B by plasma-chemical conversion of contaminated water in a dynamic mode.

1. Electrodes made of refractory alloy
2. Solution to be treated
3. Connections for water inlet and outlet
4. Power supply with a declining voltage/amperage characteristic.
5. Devices for monitoring.

The experiments were performed using the galvanostatic mode with a current of 45 A and voltages ranging from 21 to 24 V. The electrical parameters were selected to promote stable plasma torch combustion and to maintain reactor operation stability.

The solutions were processed in a temperature range of 20°--75°C. The background solution was prepared using 0.2 M K₂SO₄. K₂SO₄ was selected due to

potential interference with sodium determination in the final solution by Na salt dyes.

Model solutions of Procion red MX-5B, Sigma-Aldrich, $\lambda_{\max} = 538$ nm, were used as purification objects. The reagent was not further purified since it is used in industry in this form and is present in waste water. It has the following properties – Molecular Formula: C₁₉H₁₃Cl₂N₆NaO₇S₂, Molecular Weight: 595.37, CAS Number: 17804-49-8.

Fig. 2– Structure of Procion red MX-5B dye.

The effectiveness of the dye destruction process was monitored by measuring the decrease in the solution's color intensity over time. The initial concentration of the dye in the solution was 25 mg/L. The concentration of Procion red MX-5B in the plasma-chemical treatment process was determined using UV-visible spectroscopy. The spectra of Procion red MX-5B solutions were recorded using a Shimadzu UV2450 spectrophotometer within the wavelength range of $\lambda = 200\text{--}700$ nm. The analysis was performed using 10 mm thick quartz cuvettes. Distilled water was used as the reference solution.

The temperature was regulated and monitored during the experiment using a temperature sensor, a thermal relay, and a device that recorded the heat release curve. We conducted a qualitative analysis of decay products of Procion red MX-5B dye using a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system with a UV detector (254 nm). We used a column LiChrospher® (Merck) 100CN (5 μm) (250/4 mm, 5 μm) with hydrophobic and polar properties. We varied the mobile phase of $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ranging from 0/100 to 100/0 over 1800 seconds at a flow rate of $1.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. We measured the radiation intensity in the visible and UV ranges using an AccuMAX XRP-3000 radiometer-photometer. The radiation intensity in the UV range was determined at a wavelength of $\lambda = 365$ nm.

We measured the particle size distribution of the dispersed phase using the SOPAT method. For a detailed description of the method, refer to [7].

3. Results and discussion

Plasma-chemical cleaning combines the effects of electric field, temperature, and UV radiation on the object being treated. The alternating electric current applied to the electrodes causes the electrolysis of water, resulting in the formation of atomic oxygen and hydrogen. Furthermore, when operating the plasma chemical reactor, water molecules decompose into various radicals that form and recombine, leading to the creation of highly active intermediate compounds.

The following diagrams depict the primary schemes of radical formation and recombination:

Free radicals recombine with each other and ions present in the aqueous solution to form active compounds H_2O_2 , O_2 and H_2 according to the following schemes:

Electrochemical reactions on the electrodes produce various free radicals with both oxidizing and reducing properties. Some free radicals recombine to form water and generate heat, while others react with reactive solution components. Both oxidation and reduction reactions occur in this non-stationary process. The dye molecules undergo transformations, resulting in changes and destruction of their structure, and decomposition of some, while forming other intermediates. Heating the solution and intense UV radiation from the plasma torch facilitate the destruction of the molecules by forming reactive particles in the solution.

The plasma-chemical unit causes a significant visual change in the dye solution within the first 5-7 minutes. The changes in absorption ϵ within the 200-700 nm range, depending on treatment time, are illustrated in Figure 3. The visible region's absorption maximum (515-550 nm) that determines the dye's red colour decreases gradually (see Figure 3).

Fig. 3 – The absorption spectra of Procion red MX-5B dye in the UV and visible regions as a function of treatment time (minutes).

This process corresponds to the decomposition of the chromophore diazo group $N=N$ in the dye molecule. In the UV region of the spectrum, the decay of the diazogroup corresponds to a decrease in absorption in the 290-310 nm range [5]. The dye molecule decomposes into two fragments; fragment 1 consists of a benzene ring, and fragment 2 consists of a naphthalene and triazine ring. At the same time, hydrolysis of sulfo groups in aromatic rings occurs. The continued destruction of fragments 1 and 2 is likely to result in the cleavage of the triazine ring and the production of oxidation

products of the benzene and naphthalene rings, ultimately leading to the destruction of fragment 2. The breakdown of aromatic rings is linked to variations in absorption in the 270-275 nm range [5, 6] and occurs at a slower rate than that of the chromophore diazogroup $N=N$. A 27% decline in absorbance in the 270-275 nm range was observed 20 minutes after treatment, causing the formation of aromatic fragments 1 and 2 (Fig. 3), which also absorb UV radiation in this range. Subsequently, the formation of quinone, naphthoquinone, benzoic acid, muconic acid, and other compounds may occur.

Fig. 4– Possible mechanisms for the degradation of Procion red MX-5B in a plasma reactor.

Simultaneously, the absorption maxima shift to the corresponding parts of the spectrum for the formed structures of destruction intermediates, as depicted in Figure 4. Plasmochemical destruction of Procion red MX-5B is nearly complete within 20 minutes. Further

degradation is significantly slower and infeasible due to the subsequent rise in power consumption. It is recommended to combine plasma chemical treatment with biodegradation techniques.

Table 1

The degradation products of the dye were observed after 30 minutes of plasma-chemical treatment

Chemical structure	Retention time, min.
<p>Chemical structure of a naphthalene derivative. It features a naphthalene ring system with a hydroxyl group (OH) at position 1, an amino group (NH₂) at position 2, and sulfonate groups (SO₃⁻) at positions 4 and 7.</p>	1.67
<p>Chemical structure of benzoic acid, consisting of a benzene ring with a carboxylic acid group (COOH) attached.</p>	1.75
<p>Chemical structure of benzaldehyde, consisting of a benzene ring with an aldehyde group (CHO) attached.</p>	2.21
<p>Chemical structure of benzyl alcohol, consisting of a benzene ring with a hydroxymethyl group (CH₂OH) attached.</p>	2.45
<p>Chemical structure of benzophenone, consisting of a benzene ring with a carbonyl group (C=O) attached.</p>	3.85
<p>Chemical structure of a complex dye derivative. It features a naphthalene ring system with a hydroxyl group (OH) at position 1, a sulfonate group (SO₃Na) at position 4, and a sulfonate group (SO₃Na) at position 7. It also has a benzylidene group (C=N-Ph) at position 2 and a 2,4-dichlorophenylamino group (NH-C₆H₃(Cl)₂) at position 8.</p>	12.6

The compounds formed during the breakdown of the dye molecule are not highly toxic and can be successfully neutralized by biological treatment methods.

Figure 5 shows the changes in the intensity of visible and UV radiation during the destruction of the dye. The intensity decreases in the first minutes of the plasma-chemical module operation. This is due to the formation of a large number of carbon-containing dye degradation products in the solution, which have colloidal dimensions and absorb a significant part of the

radiation in the visible and UV spectra. The curve for the UV spectrum is less sloping, which is associated with the destruction of the dye and a decrease in its contribution to the total absorption of UV radiation. After 15 minutes of cell operation, a slight increase in radiation intensity is observed due to sedimentation and floating of degradation products. The solution gradually brightens.

Fig.5 – Changes in the intensity of visible (dashed line, left scale) and UV radiation (solid line, right scale)

Two types of carbon-containing degradation products are formed. The first one is a finely dispersed hydrophobic material that, due to its low specific gravity, hydrophobicity and the inclusion of gas bubbles, floats and concentrates near the solution-air interface. The second type consists of larger and more hydrophilic particles and accumulates in the lower part of the cell by sedimentation.

Their particle size distribution is illustrated in Figure 6. As can be seen from the above integrated size

distribution curves, the sediment consists of large conglomerates, the vast majority of carbonaceous material in it is larger than 50 microns, so it is rapidly sedimented with enlargement and formation of large conglomerates. Some carbonaceous material that floats to the surface of the water-air interface is much smaller. Particles with a size of 1 to 5 microns predominate, while at the same time, smaller particles of the order of hundreds of nanometers are quite visible.

Fig.6 – The carbon material's particle size distribution obtained by plasma-chemical conversion of the Procion red MX-5B dye is shown by the solid curve on the surface and the dashed curve in the precipitate.

4. Conclusions

The plasmochemical destruction of Procion red MX-5B was studied. A plasma electrochemical unit with a modified plasma generating module was used to treat wastewater contaminated with the dye. The concentration of Procion red MX-5B during plasma treatment was determined by UV-visible spectroscopy. The spectra of Procion red MX-5B solutions were recorded on a Shimadzu UV2450 spectrophotometer, wavelength range $\lambda = 200\text{-}700\text{ nm}$.

It was found that plasma-chemical treatment of Procion red MX-5B dye causes rapid destruction of its molecule. At the first stage, the molecule splits into two aromatic fragments. Subsequently, the degradation of intermediate aromatic compounds begins. The resulting decomposition products have low toxicity and can be successfully neutralised by biological treatment methods. In the future, it is planned to study the degradation of dye decomposition intermediates in more detail and to investigate the possibility of their neutralisation by combining plasmochemical destruction with further biological treatment.

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